

can only occur in borderline cases. It should eventually improve data processing and interpretation.

To apply this method, estimate the

exact area of the plot and then the area of azolla cover. First ask: "Does azolla cover more or less than 50% of the area?" Continue to estimate

according to the scale. The same scale (except for level 6) can be used to estimate area covered by rice and by different weed species. □

Urea timing and application method in direct-seeded lowland rice

P.K. Mahapatra, K. Maity, and D. Lenka, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar 751003, Orissa, India

A trial tested time and method of applying urea N on waterlogged (up to 50 cm submergence) direct-seeded rice during the 1984 and 1985 wet seasons under rainfed conditions. OR117-8 (160 d) seed was broadcast on sandy clay loam (pH 5.1, 0.045% total N, 7 kg Olsen P/ha, and 50 kg K/ha). At sowing, 11 kg P/ha and 21 kg K/ha were applied uniformly. N as urea was applied at 50 kg/ha (see table).

Cured urea was prepared by mixing prilled urea 1:5 with moist soil and incubating 48 h in the shade. The rate of cured urea N was based on N added to the moist soil. When sufficient

Effect of urea and cured urea on grain yield of rice, Bhubaneswar, India.

Treatment ^a	Yield (t/ha)		
	1984	1985	Mean
Control (no N)	3.3	2.6	2.9
100% N at seeding as PU	4.0	4.1	4.0
100% N at seeding as CU	4.3	3.7	4.0
50% N as PU at seeding + 50% N as PU through spray	4.0	3.6	3.8
50% N as CU at seeding + 50% N as PU through spray	3.9	3.2	3.5
50% N as PU at seeding + 25% at 30 DAS + 25% at panicle initiation (PI)	4.4	3.7	4.0
50% N as CU at seeding + 25% at 30 DAS + 25% at PI	4.1	3.6	3.8
50% N as PU at 40 DAS + 25% at 61 DAS + 25% at PI	5.0	4.5	4.1
50% N at CU at 40 DAS + 25% at 61 DAS + 25% at PI	4.4	3.1	4.0
CD (0.05)	0.6	0.7	—

^a PU = prilled urea, CU = cured urea.

rainwater became available, the seedbed was plowed down by a wooden country plow followed by planking (a common practice in Orissa) at 30 d after sowing (DAS). Weeding and gapfilling were done at 40 DAS.

Application of 50% N at 40 DAS plus 25% at 61 DAS and 25% at panicle initiation gave the highest grain yield in both years. Applying 100% N as urea at seeding gave consistently good yields. Cured urea proved to be inferior to prilled urea. □

An improved method of representative sampling from aerobic soil solutions

D.K. Kundu, F.N. Ponnampereuma, and H. U. Neue, Soil Chemistry Department, IRRRI

Analysis of a soil solution collected in situ from aerobic soil can be used for soil chemical environment analyses. However, it is difficult to obtain a sample from aerobic soils with moisture contents near field capacity (FC). The displacement method for well-packed FC moist soil columns has not been tested for validity under normal pot culture conditions. We evaluated samples collected by the conventional displacement method from three FC potted soils with different densities.

Twelve kilograms each of air-dried

(>2 mm sized) Luisiana clay, Maahas clay, and Pila loam soils were placed in 16-liter porcelain pots fitted at the bottom with drainage (coarse sintered glass) tubes. The soils were brought to FC moisture using tensiometers.

To collect soil solutions, 0.5% KSCN as displacing solution was poured on the soil surfaces. The displaced solutions were drained into measuring cylinders. We tested the collected solutions for SCN-ion at regular intervals. Drops of acidic FeCl₃ solution were used as the indicator (a blood red-colored complex is formed).

From the fast-draining Luisiana clay and Pila loam soils, we could collect only 20-30 ml of soil solution. Beyond this volume, the leachate was diluted by the displacement solution. In slow-draining Maahas clay, no displacement fluid appeared in the first 200 ml.

About 175 ml of soil solution is needed for a complete analysis; the displacement method was not appropriate for soils with fast drainage properties.

In a second experiment, we compared soil solution collected by the displacement method with equilibrated saturation extracts of three soils. Equilibrium was ensured by recycling the saturation extracts three times. Saturating a soil to FC, then immediately draining it does not give equilibrium extract. Allowing FC soils to remain saturated for a long time (beyond 8 h in many cases) might cause soil reduction.

We used three soils set up as in the first experiment, replicated six times. Demineralized water, in volumes required to bring the FC soils to saturation, was poured on the soil surface. The first 125-ml leachates